

Topological changes and deformation mechanisms of nanoporous Ta under compression

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Abstract

While the mechanical behavior of noble nanoporous metals has been the subject of numerous studies, less is known about their recently developed refractory-based counterparts. Here we report on the mechanical properties, deformation mechanisms and topological changes of nanoporous tantalum, a prototypical refractory metal, by means of atomistic simulations of compression tests. An open-source multi-cpu and gpu-capable software is presented and used for the generation of computational samples. The stress strain curves show a non-linear elastic response, with early yielding. The plastic regime is first characterized by a linear hardening followed by an exponential hardening at large strains, associated with a high degree of densification. Plasticity is dominated by dislocation activity, with twinning and vacancy formation appearing as complementary deformation mechanisms. In order to study the mechanical response from a topological perspective, we track the evolution of the genus throughout the tests, finding direct correlations with each regime of the stress strain curves. The results are in agreement with previous studies of plasticity in nanoporous metals and highlight the importance of using topological metrics, for gaining insights into complex aspects of the deformation of nanoporous metals.

1. Introduction

Nanoporous (np) metals offer a vast range of applications. This includes unique performance for catalytic and optical applications due to its high surface-to-volume ratio [1, 2]. In addition, their development opened the door for the fabrication of surface-chemistry-powered actuators and sensors, among other cutting-edge technology [3, 4]. The range of potential applications extends to materials for advanced fission and fusion reactors [5–8]. Studies on the mechanical properties of nanoporous metals typically deal with noble metals, most notably nanoporous gold (np-Au) [9–24]. Despite the remarkable properties of np-Au, its thermal instability [25] and propensity to coarsening [26] limits practical applications.

The development of modern dealloying techniques opened the door for the fabrication of new non-noble nanoporous metals, such those made of refractory metals. Important examples from a technological application perspective include np-W, np-Ta, np-Mo and np-Nb [27–33]. Despite their potential, experiments on mechanical characterization of such materials is generally lacking, with a notable exception after the work of Zhao et al. [34, 35], who used nanoindentation testing to probe the mechanical properties of np-W with relatively high solid fraction (above 0.484). Their studies show that np-W is a high performance material, with a high

hardness (several GPa), highlighting its potential applications in harsh environments, such as nuclear facilities.

The mechanical properties of macroporous foams are typically dictated by the relative density and characteristics of its base material. In contrast, the mechanical properties of nanoporous metals are not only dictated by the former, but also by their ligament size [10], surface effects [36] and network connectivity [37] among other topological aspects [38, 39].

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, despite timescale and lengthscale limitations, have proven to be a valuable tool for studying the mechanical response of nanoporous metals. Two notable contributions serve as examples. The first one is that of Farkas et al. [13], who first reported on tension-compression asymmetry for nanoporous gold, confirmed experimentally several years later [19]. The second one is that of Bringa et al. [5], who showed that nanoporous metals can display radiation tolerance depending on irradiation conditions and ligament size, opening a new line of application for these materials [6]. In addition, the MD technique has been used to provide important insights into a variety of effects. A non-exhaustive list includes ligament size effects [40, 41], strain-rate effects [42, 43], grain size effects [40, 44], temperature effects [45], anomalous compliance and early yielding [46], densification and hardening [16, 41] and load-bearing network and topological effects [47–49]. The technique has even been used to derive and inform scaling laws [12, 22, 50] and also to provide fundamental explanations on np-Au fracture [51]. More recently, it has provided valuable insights into the mechanical response of graded nanoporous structures [52] and hierarchical nanoporous structures [53].

The knowledge on the mechanical properties of nanoporous refractory metals is still in its infancy compared to that of noble metals, for which much has been investigated using nanoporous gold [24]. Differences in its base material, slip systems, dislocation interaction and storage are expected to play an important role in the mechanical response. However, these aspects have not been deeply investigated so far and are brought into focus in this study. In fact, dislocation accumulation in nanoporous gold has been linked to its hardening behavior under compression, together with uniform densification. It can be expected that if densification takes place, the connectivity of the foam would change and if so, the strain hardening behavior of nanoporous foams could be correlated to changes in its topology. This leads to the conjecture that alterations in the foam’s topology, stemming from the occurrence of densification, may significantly influence the strain hardening behavior of nanoporous foams. Here we test this hypothesis employing surface reconstruction techniques and common topological metrics.

In this work, we explore the mechanical response, deformation mechanism and topology evolution during compression of nanoporous tantalum, a prototypical refractory metal. An open-source multi-cpu and gpu-capable software is presented and used for the generation of computational samples. We perform MD-simulated compression tests up to large strains, in excess of 60 percent, fully exploring the elastic regime, linear hardening regime and exponential densification regime. In addition to the inspection of the deformation mechanisms, we present an analysis of the evolution of topology during deformation. Finally, we correlate the different hardening stages with notorious changes in the topology of the foams.

2. Computational modeling

2.1. Code for generation of nanoporous samples

Nanoporous tantalum produced by liquid-metal dealloying can be classified as an open-cell foam with nanoscale features [29]. It shows striking similarities with nanoporous gold produced by dealloying [1, 6, 54], resembling those structures associated with spinodal decomposition [55]. Initial attempts to study nanoporous gold with MD simulations relied on sample generation by means of phase-field methods [56, 57]. More recently, the development of levelled-wave methods based on Cahn’s equation [58, 59], and even fully molecular dynamics methods based on Ag-Au

demixing [60] resulted in a significant increase of studies of np metals using MD simulations. In this work, we employ an in-house implementation of the levelled-wave method presented by Soyarslan et al. [58]. This method has been successfully applied in a number of studies [26, 48, 49, 52, 53]. For completeness, the method is briefly described below.

In 1965, Cahn presented the theory of phase separation from a single phase fluid by a spinodal mechanism. He showed that the predicted structure may be described in terms of the superposition of an infinite number of sinusoidal waves of a fixed wavelength, but random in amplitude, orientation, and phase [61]. More recently, Soyarslan et al. [58] explore a modern implementation of this random field f :

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} \sum_{i=1}^N \cos(\mathbf{q}_i \cdot \mathbf{x} + \varphi_i). \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the position vector, N is the number of waves considered on the truncated series, while \mathbf{q}_i and φ_i denote the direction and phase of the wave i , respectively. The wave number must be set to a constant value (i.e. $|\mathbf{q}_i| = q_0$), with directions uniformly distributed over a 4π solid angle, and phases uniformly distributed between 0 and 2π . Under this constraints, $f(\mathbf{x})$ is a random gaussian field with $\langle f \rangle = 0$ and $\langle f^2 \rangle = 1$. Provided N is sufficiently large, the value $f(\mathbf{x})$ for a given position \mathbf{x} follows a Gaussian distribution:

$$P(f) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-f^2/2}, \quad (2)$$

and the mean wave direction

$$\nu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{n}_i \quad (3)$$

tends to zero as consequence of the central limit theorem. Therefore, f is an isotropic function.

For equation (1), the different phases of the system are obtained by means of a cutoff value ξ :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{B} & \quad \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}) < \xi, \\ \mathbf{x} \in \partial\mathcal{B} & \quad \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}) = \xi, \\ \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{P} & \quad \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}) > \xi. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, \mathcal{B} is the solid phase, \mathcal{P} is the porous phase and $\partial\mathcal{B}$ is the boundary between the two phases. ξ can be correlated to the solid fraction, defined as $\phi_{\mathcal{B}} := |\mathcal{B}|/|\mathcal{V}|$ (the ratio of the volume of the solid phase to the total volume of the sample), thanks to the properties of the random Gaussian field:

$$\xi(\phi_{\mathcal{B}}) = \sqrt{2} \operatorname{erf}^{-1}(2\phi_{\mathcal{B}} - 1), \quad (5)$$

The structures generated using eqns. (1) and (4) are, in general, non periodic. Periodicity can be obtained by choosing a finite number of waves with an integer wave number in all directions, with constant modulus.

Starting from (1), with $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$ unit vectors of an orthonormal base in real space, \mathbf{q}_i must be of the form

$$\mathbf{q} = \frac{2\pi}{A}(h, k, l), \quad (6)$$

where $h, k, l \in \mathbb{Z}$ correspond to Miller indexes and A is a constant. It can be verified that $f(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x} + n_1 A \mathbf{e}_1 + n_2 A \mathbf{e}_2 + n_3 A \mathbf{e}_3)$, with n_1, n_2 y n_3 arbitrary integers. This implies

that f is periodic with magnitude A with respect to the base. Moreover, if (1) is taken with identical ϕ_i , then f is also invariant with respect to an axis interchange. So the resulting f has cubic symmetry with grid parameter A . Based on the aforementioned considerations, periodic stochastic structures can be built by restricting the sum on eqn. (1) to a set of \mathbf{q}_i with a given value and constant H , so that

$$H = \sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}, \quad (7)$$

with $|\mathbf{q}| = q_0 = 2\pi H/A$.

For structures with equal fraction of the two phases, symmetry suggests that the average ligament size is equal to the average pore size:

$$L = 1.23 \frac{\pi}{q_0} \quad (8)$$

For nanoporous structures with solid fraction different than 0.5, the average ligament size of the solid phase is given by:

$$L = \frac{A}{H} [0.53\phi_B + 0.41]. \quad (9)$$

For more details on the method, the reader is referred to [58, 61].

While the implementation of the method is straightforward by means of nested-loop programming, such approach is not practical given memory and wall-time limitations. Therefore, we opted for a more elaborated approach. We define a rank-3 tensor

$$T_{ijk} := (\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{x})_{ij} + \phi_k, \quad (10)$$

for all points \mathbf{x} of the domain and for all \mathbf{q} wave vectors on the set of directions. The implementation makes use of *NumPy*¹. In order to avoid memory limitations, the T_{ijk} tensor was decomposed into smaller tensors. Such segmentation allows for multi-core parallelization using *joblib*² and *loky*³ libraries. Finally, the code was also implemented on GPUs using *Tensorflow 2* framework⁴. Benchmarking of the code is presented in section 8. The code is provided open-source⁵.

2.2. Nanoporous samples and their relaxation

The method explained in the previous section was used to produce stochastic bicontinuous structures of two phases, α and β . Equation 4 was sampled at the atomic locations of a [100]-oriented Ta single crystal and all atoms located in phase α – as determined by the threshold parameter ξ – were removed to create pores, with the nanoscale porous structure resulting from the remaining phase β atoms. The samples were generated using periodic boundary conditions, with a lattice parameter $a_0 = 0.3303 \text{ nm}$, $N = 20000$ waves, $H^2 = 161$ and a solid fraction $\phi_B \approx 0.3$. We generated three virtual np structures, each with a different ligament size, see Table 1.

Prior to the simulation of mechanical tests, each foam was first minimized by the conjugate gradient method specifying a force tolerance of $10^{-8} \text{ eV/\text{Angstrom}}$ and an energy tolerance of 10^{-6} eV . Then the structure was thermally relaxed at 300 K for 500 ps and zero pressure using a NPT ensemble. Periodic boundary conditions were imposed in all directions. The simulations were performed using LAMMPS [63] and the Ta atomic interactions were modeled by means of an extended Finnis-Sinclair potential (EFS) [64]. This potential successfully reproduces lattice

¹<https://numpy.org/>

²<https://joblib.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

³<https://github.com/joblib/loky>

⁴<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁵https://github.com/nicolasvazquez95/Nanofams_Creator

Simulation domain	Atoms	L_{box} (nm)	As-generated		After relaxation		Mechanical properties	
			ϕ_B	L (nm)	ϕ_B	L (nm)	E (GPa)	σ_y (MPa)
150 a_0	2.3 10^6	49.5	0.291	2.26	0.294	2.4	1.80	89.3
200 a_0	5.5 10^6	66	0.301	3.1	0.303	3.1	1.83	91.0
250 a_0	10.3 10^6	82.5	0.297	3.78	0.298	3.8	2.18	98.4

Table 1: Summary of sample characteristics and dimensions. These correspond to the as-generated samples (i.e. before relaxation). Relative densities were computed using the *ConstructSurfaceMesh* algorithm implemented in OVITO. Average ligament sizes L were computed using FoamExplorer [62].

constants, cohesive energies, elastic constants and vacancy formation energies of Ta [64]. The generalized stacking faults energy curves and generalized twinning fault energy curves had been thoroughly studied [65–67] and compared to other Ta potentials [67]. The potential has proven useful in describing dislocation-mediated plasticity in closed-cell nanoporous Ta under tension and compression [65, 66, 68, 69], as well as bulk Ta under spherical nanoindentation [67].

As a result of the minimization and relaxation strategy, a small amount of ligament coarsening and a reduction of the sample dimensions was verified, and the updated dimensions are presented on Table 1. These correspond to converged values, i.e. they remained unaltered during the last 200 ps of the relaxation stage. Relaxation of the initially rigid and defect-free porous crystal in the absence of mechanical loading led to samples with a number of dislocations (Fig. 1). Similar defects had been reported after transmission electron micrographs of nanoporous gold produced by dealloying [70].

As a result of the whole procedure, we were able to generate open-cell np-Ta atomistic samples with pre-existing defects, that closely resembles np-Ta foams produced by liquid-metal dealloying [29], combining nanoscale ligaments and pores. According to [58], the generated microstructures can be considered as representative volume elements (RVEs) given the parameters used on their generation.

Figure 1: a) Plan view of the largest sample generated (Simulation domain $250 a_0$, $L_{box} = 82.5$ nm, Scale bar 20 nm) compared to a nanoporous Ta sample produced by liquid metal dealloying (Reprinted from [29], with permission from Elsevier). b) Dislocation (green) nucleated during relaxation on a ligament junction (circle). c) Another example of dislocation generated during relaxation.

2.3. Simulation details

Uniaxial compression tests were simulated with the loading axis aligned to the z-axis. A thermostat and barostat were used to maintain lateral pressure (x and y directions) at approximately 0 Pa and to keep temperature constant at 300K. Mimicking strain-controlled compressive mechanical deformation tests, each sample was uniaxially compressed along the [001]-direction by re-scaling its z-dimension at a strain rate of 1×10^8 s⁻¹ with a 2 fs timestep. Stresses are presented in the form of von Mises stress. LAMMPS output of the stress tensor of the simulation box is σ_{ij} from which the scalar quantity σ_{VM} can be computed as:

$$\sigma_{VM} = \sqrt{\sigma_{xx}^2 + \sigma_{yy}^2 + \sigma_{zz}^2 - (\sigma_{xx}\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{xx}\sigma_{zz} + \sigma_{yy}\sigma_{zz}) + 3(\sigma_{xy} + \sigma_{xz} + \sigma_{yz})} \quad (11)$$

Post-processing was performed using OVITO [71] and the Crystal Analysis Tool [72], thus allowing for detailed defect identification and tracking.

3. Results

3.1. Stress - strain curves

Figure 2 (top) presents the stress-strain curves for the three samples studied. Figure 3 presents an extract of the stress- strain curve focusing on the elastic regime and the early

stages of plasticity. Noticeable features included a non-linear elastic regime (3), as well as early-yielding. Both behaviors had been previously reported for nanoporous gold [24, 46].

Table 1 presents the elastic modulus E and yield stress σ_Y obtained for our samples. The former was obtained from the stress strain response during the first 0.01 strain. The latter was taken as the intersection of the stress strain curve with a parallel line offset by 0.01 strain, its slope being E . Both elastic modulus and yield strength decrease with ligament size, in a *smaller is weaker* fashion. This is attributed to the ligament size range explored (below 5 nm), akin to an inverse Hall-Petch effect.

Figure 2: *Top* von Mises stress - strain plot for the three samples studied, according to their average ligament size. *Bottom* Dimensionless genus per volume ratio (g_V/g_V^0) for the three samples studied.

All simulations present a linear hardening regime for strains below 0.4. While hardening is typically absent for macroporous foams [73], it is not new for nanoporous metals. Linear hardening in nanoporous Au under compression is known to be ligament size-dependent. This was first reported in experiments [74], but can also be found in molecular dynamics simulation literature [41]. In our case, all three samples display a similar linear hardening stage, almost overlapping, most likely due to ligament sizes within the same order of magnitude, unlike in [41, 74]. Under compression, nanoporous metals typically densify uniformly, leading to a continuous hardening response [74]. As a consequence, the onset of densification regime is ill-defined for nanoporous metals, and it is known to vary with ligament size. That is clearly seen in our curves. Samples with smaller ligament size densify earlier than those with larger ligament size, in agreement with experimental findings for np-Au [24]. Interestingly, the exponential

Figure 3: Early stage of the von Mises stress - strain plot for the three samples studied, according to their average ligament size.

hardening regime shows a noticeable ligament size dependence, and will be further discussed in Sec. 3.3.

3.2. Deformation mechanisms

Initially and up to moderate strains, our simulations reveal that nanoporous Ta deforms by ligament bending with plastic collapse at the ligament nodes or close to them (Figure 4). Plasticity mainly proceeds by dislocation activity. Nucleation takes place at free surfaces in the form of glissile dislocations (Figure 4.a,b). They propagate across the ligaments and annihilate at nearby surfaces. These corresponds to dislocations with Burgers vector $\vec{b} = \frac{a_0}{2}\langle 111 \rangle$. Despite the abundance of free surfaces that act as dislocation sinks, deformation proceeds in a dislocation accumulation scenario, in agreement with experimental and computational studies on nanoporous gold [16, 74]. It must be noted that under creep conditions, np-Au MD studies suggest that nanoporous metals can deform by displacive-diffusion mechanisms [75]. We found no indications of such mechanism, most probably due to the high strain-rate conditions and short timescales explored.

In addition to surface exhaustion mechanisms, a fraction of dislocations get retained inside the ligaments. Such retention is favored at ligament junctions, where dislocations have enough space for reaction with other dislocations, promoting junction formation as well as the generation of sessile dislocations ($\vec{b} = a_0\langle 100 \rangle$) by the following reaction,

$$\frac{1}{2}\langle 1\bar{1}\bar{1} \rangle + \frac{1}{2}\langle \bar{1}\bar{1}1 \rangle \rightarrow \langle 0\bar{1}0 \rangle \quad (12)$$

Prominent examples of the aforementioned mechanism can be seen on Figure 5.a. It is also shown that vacancy formation also takes place due to the reaction of dislocations (Figure 5.b).

Figure 4: Dislocation activity. (a,b) At a strain of 0.1, few dislocations are noticeable on some ligaments. Most of the generated dislocations have reached nearby surfaces, effectively annihilating. (c,d) At a strain of 0.4, a large number of dislocations are seen, mainly on ligament junctions. These are glissile dislocations (green - $\vec{b} = \frac{a_0}{2} \langle 111 \rangle$) and sessile dislocations (pink - $\vec{b} = a_0 \langle 100 \rangle$). Note that the densification has started.

It is likely that self-interstitials get generated too. However, we failed to identify them. In MD simulations, self-interstitials are generally identified by means of a Wigner-Seitz analysis [76] comparing a deformed configuration against an undeformed one. Such a comparison was not possible here due to the significant amount of deformation. It must also be noted that point defect generation might be influenced by strain-rate effects [77].

Figure 5: Dislocation junctions in a region with high dislocation density. Reaction of dislocations of glissile dislocations ($\vec{b} = \frac{a_0}{2}\langle 111 \rangle$, green) lead to the generation of sessile dislocations ($\vec{b} = a_0\langle 100 \rangle$, pink). Dislocation reactions also promote vacancy generation. Arrows indicate Burgers vector. Reconstructed surfaces of the foam are not displayed to favor the visualization of dislocations. Red clusters correspond to vacancies.

Figure 6 presents an evolution of the total dislocation length for our largest sample. In addition, the total length is discriminated considering the burgers vector of the dislocations. It can be seen that $\langle 111 \rangle$ glissile dislocations dominate, followed by $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 110 \rangle$ sessile dislocations. Dislocations with different burgers vector are also identified by the algorithm (type 'Other'). However, detailed inspection of them reveals that the mostly have a burgers vector proportional to one of the previous three categories, while others are assigned a burgers vector not consistent with dislocations in bcc metals pointing to possible artifacts in the identification of dislocations in heavily strained configurations. Similar trends were observed for all the samples simulated here.

A small fraction of twinning was also found, see Figure 7. Tantalum is known to deform by twinning under high strain-rate compression [78]. High strain-rate conditions are inherent to MD simulations when exploring uniaxial compression of metals and therefore, this finding is not surprising. Experimental studies of nanoporous Ta at low strain rates are necessary to determine if twinning takes place in absence of high strain rates.

Figure 6: Evolution of total dislocation length for our largest sample tested ($250 a_0$, $L = 3.8 \text{ nm}$). Contributions to the total length include $\langle 111 \rangle$ -type glissile dislocations, $\langle 110 \rangle$ -type and $\langle 100 \rangle$ -type sessile dislocations and 'Other'-type dislocations, as described in Sec. 3.2.

Figure 7: Example of a twin generated during deformation. (a) Atoms colored according to local structural environment: blue (bcc), red (twin boundaries), white (*other*). (b) Atoms colored according to degree of rotation. Continuous lines indicate ligament surfaces. Dashed lines indicate twin boundaries. Note the rotation of the atoms between them.

3.3. Topological evolution during deformation

A positive aspect of atomistic simulations is that they allow for detailed tracking of atomic positions and microstructures. In this way, and making use of surface reconstruction algorithms [79], it is possible to track the evolution of the topology throughout the simulated compression test.

At all stages of deformation, the surface of the sample can be determined by surface reconstruction techniques. Here we used the Gaussian density method, as implemented in OVITO [80]. Detailed information on the reconstructed surface mesh is readily available. This includes: number of vertices (V), number of edges (E) and number of faces (F) forming the reconstructed closed surface. This allows computing the Euler characteristic (χ) as

$$\chi = V - E + F \quad (13)$$

For a closed surface, the Euler characteristic is equivalent to the genus (g) through:

$$g = 1 - \frac{\chi}{2} \quad (14)$$

This is a metric of the surface connectivity; it can be interpreted as the number of continuous holes, or handles, on the resulting manifold made by the closed surface.

The determination of χ and g after the reconstructed surface of the nanoporous sample is a valid procedure used both in experimental approaches, through FIB-nanotomography methods [81], and in molecular dynamics studies [60].

In order to take into account volume changes, the genus is often normalized by the total volume of the foam and scaled using a characteristic length to produce a non-dimensional quantity [58]. We normalized the genus by the sample volume $g_V = g/V$. Then, by taking the ratio of genus g_V/g_V^0 , g_V^0 being the genus per volume in the absence of strain, we obtain the results in a non-dimensional form.

Figure 2 presents a correlation of the stress strain curves (a), with the g_V/g_V^0 ratio (b). Interestingly, the evolution of the genus ratio for the three samples also overlaps for the same strain regime that the stress strain curves do. Most importantly, the genus increases during the linear hardening regime and that increase starts right after the onset of plasticity, indicating that continuous densification is present through out this regime.

As the deformation of the foam enters the plastic regime, the foam experiences a compaction where more and more ligaments become into contact. As more ligaments become into contact, then one would expect that more cuttings would be needed to produce a disconnected manifold. This can be seen on Figure 4 by comparing panels b) and d). Such behavior holds until strains of 0.4 (small sample - $L = 2.4 \text{ nm}$) to 0.5 (large sample - $L = 3.8 \text{ nm}$) are reached.

For larger strains, the evolution of the genus shifts and starts decreasing. Notable differences in genus are also consistent with stress strain curves differentiation in the exponential densification regime, indicating variations in the densification rate. Note that the genus data is presented up to a strain of the order of 0.55. After that strain, the reconstructed surface is no longer closed, thus preventing the computation of genus over the whole sample. Analysis of the reconstructed surfaces reveals that, at such large strains, porosity is now distributed in the form of disconnected voids. The reconstructed surfaces we obtain at very high strains are indeed disconnected, as seen on Figure 8. This is correlated to a change of the foam from its original open-cell nature, to a partially closed-cell structure.

Figure 8: Reconstructed surface for the largest sample tested ($250 a_0$, $L = 3.8 \text{ nm}$). a) Undeformed state showing the free surfaces of the ligaments. b) At a strain of 0.7, the porous phase is no longer continuous. The sides of the box show a significant compaction of the foam, yet not fully densified. In fact, the interior of sample presents isolated voids in the material. The porous phase is now discontinuous and pores with different volume can be appreciated. In order to enhance the visibility, a number of interior surfaces were removed.

4. Discussion

The mechanical properties of nanoporous metals have often been studied using nanoporous gold as a prototypical example. Our results also show significant points of agreement with previous studies on that material. To begin with, the response clearly depicts three regimes, namely an elastic regime, a linear hardening regime, and an exponential regime, consistent with previous reports on np-Au [41, 46, 74]. Deformation proceeds by ligament bending and plasticity takes place by dislocation nucleation at the ligament surfaces, in a dislocation accumulation scenario [16, 22, 46, 47, 74]. After yielding, some np Au works display a stress plateau [13, 16] whereas others display linear hardening [41, 46]. Our results show an agreement with the latter, probably due to the ligament size and relative density explored.

Mathesan and Mordehai [48, 49] used MD simulations to explore the influence of topology on the mechanical properties of np-Au nanopillars. In particular, they focused on the load-bearing network. They show a strong influence on the elastic properties [48]. Later on, by detailed analysis of the genus of the yielded ligaments network, they conclude that the rate by which the strength increases with strain decreases gradually, in correlation with a decrease in the genus of a subnetwork of the unyielded ligaments [49]. Although our study focuses on a different base material in the form of bulk np-W (in contrast to np-Au nanopillars in [48, 49]), a general agreement can be found. That is, (i) after the onset of the plastic regime the genus increases until significant plastic strain has been reached; (ii) a correlation of the genus with the stress strain response.

The linear hardening regime has been typically associated with dislocation activity as well as densification, whereas the exponential hardening is heavily influenced by latter. This has been shown in MD simulations of nanoporous gold under compression. Ngo et al. [46] studies on np-Au provided compelling evidence pointing to dislocation storage as responsible for hardening behavior together with densification. Ruestes et al. [16] and Saffarini et al. [41] later presented more evidence and provided dislocation density-based equations relating dislocation density and solid fraction evolution. Here we provide an alternative interpretation for the different strain hardening regimes.

Figure 9 presents the evolution of the genus ration and the total dislocation density for the largest sample tested ($250 a_0$, $L = 3.8 \text{ nm}$). For interpretation purposes, the linear hardening regime and exponential hardening regime are indicated, as revealed by Fig. 2. During the linear hardening regime, dislocation density rapidly increases, together with an increase in the genus ratio. The former indicates a dislocation-accumulation scenario, whereas the latter indicates a correlation of topology with linear hardening. During the exponential hardening regime, dislocation density keeps increasing in a less marked way due to dislocation densities approaching saturation limits ($\rho_D \sim 10^{17}/\text{m}^{-2}$). Interestingly, the genus ratio drops sharply during the exponential hardening regime. These results only allow for qualitative conclusions. Specific studies are needed to provide an adequate quantitative assessment of the respective contributions of dislocations and topological changes for the two regimes.

With respect to refractory-based nanoporous metals, Xia and co-workers [82] used MD simulations to study the mechanical properties of nanoporous tungsten, another prototypical bcc metal with significant applications. By means of simulated tensile tests, they explored the effects of relative density, grain size, and temperature on the mechanical properties and deformation mechanisms of np-W. They also report on dislocation mediated plasticity, as well as on a contribution of twinning as a complementary deformation mechanism. Similar deformation mechanisms were reported by Valencia and coworkers [83] in their MD study of nanoporous W under nanoindentation. Our results are in agreement with these contributions.

Figure 9: Comparative assessment of the evolution of the genus ratio and total dislocation density for the largest sample tested ($250 a_0$, $L = 3.8 \text{ nm}$) with respect to the different hardening regimes.

5. Conclusions

In summary, we report on a computational study of the compression behavior of nanoporous Ta using molecular dynamics simulations. Computational samples were constructed using our own implementation of a levelled-wave method. This software is released as an open-source tool, with multi-cpu and gpu capabilities, allowing for fast and efficient generation of nanoporous samples. Our main conclusions are:

- Consistent with previous studies on nanoporous gold, we find that the stress strain curves depict similar qualitative features. Namely, a non-linear elastic regime, early yielding, and linear hardening followed by an exponential hardening at large strains, associated with a high degree of densification.
- Plasticity takes place by dislocation activity in the expected bcc slip systems. Even though dislocations nucleate at the surface and most of them annihilate at a nearby surface after slip through the ligaments, deformation proceeds in a dislocation accumulation scenario. Ligament junctions provide enough volume for dislocation reaction, producing sessile dislocations, as well as dislocation storage. Densification of the sample favors dislocation retention. Twinning and vacancy formation was also found.
- The evolution of the genus was successfully correlated to the stress strain behavior. Genus increases during the linear hardening regime, right after the onset of plasticity, indicating continuous densification of the sample. In contrast, the genus significantly drops at very large strains, that is during the exponential hardening regime. This is due to significant densification of the sample, shifting from an open cell foam to a closed cell foam.
- Structural changes from open-cell foam to closed-cell foam are shown to be ligament-size dependent. Our analysis indicates that, whenever possible, tracking of topological invariants (here we use g) are effective measures to characterize the evolution of the sample and could provide valuable insights for the identification of deformation-induced changes.

As a closing remark, our work suggests that fundamental understanding gained from np-Au studies is directly transferable to other nanoporous metals, albeit with differences in their deformation mechanisms. Most importantly, our analysis shows that topological metrics, genus being just one example, can provide fundamental insights into complex aspects of the deformation of nanoporous metals, such as the onset of densification and associated exponential hardening regime.

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7. Data availability statement

The computer code required to reproduce the microstructures presented here are available to download from https://github.com/nicolasvazquez95/Nanofoms_Creator. All other information is available from the authors upon a reasonable request.

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8. Appendix

8.1. Computational performance and microstructures

Figure 10 displays a limited set of microstructures generated by our implementation of the levelled-wave method [58]. For a small solid fraction ϕ_B , or for ligament sizes within the order of magnitude of the lattice parameter, it is possible to end up with a microstructure that it is below the percolation limit. In other words, the solid phase is no longer continuous [58]. For solid fractions above 0.2 and for L/L_{box} above 0.04 (L_{box} being the simulation box size), our implementation produces stochastic and fully bicontinuous microstructures.

To check the computational efficiency of our implementation, tests were performed using 4 different implementations. Figure 11 presents the results of the tests performed for the same foam input parameters (100^3 simple cubic cells, 48 directions, 10000 waves) Blue bars indicate the execution “*Walltime*” in seconds, while orange bars indicate the *speedup*. This is a metric used to measure the scalability of a computational code, defined as $\text{speedup} = \frac{t_1}{t_N}$. t_1 corresponds to the time required to run the code on a single processor, t_N is the time required on N processors. The results show a clear acceleration after the multi-CPU implementation. By recasting nested-loops into matrix operations, a GPU implementation is straightforward by means of TensorFlow packages. This last implementation displays a notorious speedup.

With the final CPU and GPU implementations, a last comparison of execution times was performed. This was done on 1 core and 16 cores for the CPU implementation. Tests were performed on TOKO FCEN UNCuyo computer cluster (1 node, AMD Ryzen 7, 64 GB Ram, 8 cores / 16 threads). The sample contained 300^3 unit cells and 20000 were used. The comparison includes walltime for a test on a K80 NVidia GPU, used over GoogleColab. Excellent performance was obtained (See Fig. 12).

Finally, our tests made use of 4GB of RAM (max) for our 16 threads CPU tests. The GPU implementation made a peak memory usage of 16 GB on the GPU plus an additional 3GB of RAM.

Figure 10: Microstructures generated with our open-source implementation of the levelled-wave method [58]. Note the percolation of the solid phase on the left hand-side column.

Figure 11: Benchmarking results using four different code versions. Numpy/CPU Tests were performed on an AMD Ryzen3 4000-series laptop. GPU tests were performed on a NVidia K80 GPU (4.1 TFlops).

Figure 12: (a) Comparison between three generation runs executed on a single core (serial), parallelly on 16 cores (multi-CPU) and on GPU. CPU characteristics: 8 cores / 16 threads, AMD Ryzen 7 processor, 64 GB RAM). GPU: NVidia K80 through GoogleColab.